

LEXICOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF "TOURISM" TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: *Theoretical lexicography deals with the history of lexicography, types of dictionaries, requirements for dictionaries, critical analysis of existing dictionaries, practical lexicography deals with the study, compilation, improvement and consumption of a certain type of vocabulary. Practical lexicography involves the application of general theoretical principles and rules of lexicography in the process of creating a dictionary. The vagueness of terms, their meanings, the essence of the notion, excessive length, complex sentences, and an excessive number of foreign terms are inconvenient. In response to the aforementioned issues, modern lexicography must create a glossary of terms in many professions. From the beginning to the finish of the terminology system development process, a lexicographer must collaborate with a specialist in the topic. This is for a variety of reasons. The lexicographer can quickly provide accurate and extensive explanations of words, as well as generate examples of authorship, when creating a dictionary of common words. As a result, monolingual dictionaries cover a greater number of terms than translation dictionaries. The functional value of the term is vital in practical translation dictionaries; that is, the user must be able to use the dictionary to grasp a specific word in the correct context, from a communication standpoint, and for himself/herself.*

Key words: *lexicography, tourism terms, bilingual dictionary, monolingual dictionary, lexicographer, equivalent.*

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, consensus on the meaning of the term lexicography and its acceptance as a science is also a recent development. Lexicography is divided into theoretical and practical elements that coexist and work in harmony. Practical lexicography deals with the research, compilation, improvement, and consumption of a certain type of vocabulary, whereas theoretical lexicography investigates the history of lexicography, types of dictionaries, prerequisites for dictionaries, and critical examination of current dictionaries. The use of general theoretical lexicographic concepts and regulations in the process of building a dictionary is known as practical lexicography.

Lexicography is a relatively new subject of study, and research in this area is insufficient when compared to other fields of linguistics. There are only twenty significant works on lexicography in the world lexicographic community, according to lexicographer L. Zgust [L. Zgusta, 1971].

Dictionaries have historically been used to not only provide information about the translation or use of a specific word, but also to broaden people's secular intercultural knowledge. Although it is well understood that different people's cultures contribute to the construction of tourism terminology as a distinct terminological system, encyclopedic knowledge about these cultures, as well as the etymology of related terms, remains an essential feature of special dictionaries. It also helps to properly comprehend the book's content, atmosphere, and the concept of "text culture." The lexicography of terms has gained a lot of attention recently. The works of I.A. Karimov, the first President of Uzbekistan, demonstrate this: "High spirituality is invincible" [Karimov I.A., 2008; 87]. Especially in such important areas as fundamental sciences, modern communication and information technologies, banking and financial systems, the use of our language, etymological and comparative dictionaries. There is no doubt that the development of the necessary terms and expressions, concepts and categories, in a word, the all-round development of the Uzbek language on a scientific basis will serve such noble goals as the awareness of national identity, a sense of homeland.

The complexity and responsibility of lexicography that was included into technical specializations could be seen from a small number of high functional value vocabularies in practice decades ago, only by looking at the ability to collect existing words and place them into a collection. Lexicography is a multidisciplinary field of study. The lexicographer must have a thorough understanding of all levels of linguistics. However, there have been high-level dictionaries developed by amateurs throughout the history of lexicography. These self-taught lexicographers are frequently experts in their fields, anticipating the wants and wishes of a true dictionary user. We proceed from the following words of L.V. Shcherba, who made a huge contribution to the creation of the theoretical foundations of this science, the hidden complexities that lie at the heart of lexicography [L.V. Scherba, 1971; 312]. Before moving on to the stage of creating a practical dictionary, let us dwell on the problems of modern terminology and topical issues.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Achievements of science and technology, as well as the development of the socio-political and economic life of countries require a constant expansion of the

vocabulary of languages, the addition of new lexical units and obsolescence of obsolete ones. Sometimes new units enter the dictionary under the new name of an existing concept. E.A. Zemskaya points out how difficult it is to learn new words when they are not associated with old ones, and that the relationship of words in a language is a reflection of the relationship between the real object of existence and events [Zemskaya E.A., 1963]. It is a process that, like general tokens, is also associated with terminology. Already, terms form the bulk of incoming new words. The prospects for science and technology and the improvement of terminology are interdependent phenomena of a proportional nature. After all, while science and technology provide a variety of terminology systems, the voluntary field of science and technology, which lacks its own theoretically based advanced terminology system, is in decline. Thus, the finalization and regulation of terminology in each area remains one of the urgent problems of modern lexicography.

The lexicography of terms, on the other hand, is a very new element of theoretical and practical lexicography, and it still has a lot of issues. Problems with terminology in all areas, as discussed by Russian linguist D.S. Lotte several decades ago, are still one of the most painful aspects of modern lexicography [Lotte D.S., 1961]:

1. The first issue is related to term ambiguity, which can be found in any industry's terminological system. In truth, terms should convey the nature of the concept in a specific area, and their reach should be limited to that area. Their distinguishing quality is that they are unambiguous and lack emotional expressive connotations, which sets them apart from conventional words. Indeed, the lexical meaning of the terms also requires this (the term comes from the Latin word *terminus*, meaning "border", "boundary marker", "restriction" [U.Sharipova, I.Yuldoshev, 2006; 50]).

2. The definition of phrases is the second pressing issue. As a result, their consumption is characterized by abstraction and ambiguity. In reality, the evolution of society necessitates the exclusion of one of the major alternatives from the vocabulary during sociocultural selection. In this situation, an option that does not adequately convey the content of the concept it expresses or causes inconvenient behavior in the program goes out of usage (due to the fact that it consists of graphics, a sound shell, a large number of components). However, this will take some time. As a result, terminological dictionaries are updated and revised on a regular basis.

3. The next problem arises due to the fact that a specific term does not fully correspond to the essence of the concept it represents. The reason is to consider the translation of terms from a foreign language as an artificial and technical process, and not to be creative. As a result, the term loses its functional value and is depreciated. The scope of the terms introduced should be limited, clear and understandable and applied consistently in this voluntary context.

4. Another disadvantage of synchronizing with the aforementioned issue is the inconvenient nature of complex phrases. However, this problem is significantly less severe than in earlier decades. The perception and knowledge of other languages (particularly English) among the middle class has improved recently. As a result, we are now familiar with many foreign phonetic terms. This is mostly a contribution to science and technology advancement (especially the Internet).

5. Another issue in lexicography that is unacceptably problematic is the overabundance of foreign terminology in terminological systems. However, this lexicographic viewpoint has become more liberalized in recent years, with the major goal now being to establish functional equivalency in the assimilation of foreign concepts. If a foreign alternative evokes a clearer grasp of a notion in the minds of customers than the "Uzbek" version of terms that reflect a specific concept, for example, it should be prioritized. After all, in the creation of terminological dictionaries, customer choice is critical.

In response to the aforementioned issues, modern lexicography must create a glossary of terms in many professions.

RESULTS

The microcomposition problems of a special dictionary are associated with the choice of lexicographic details of the actual dictionary entry. A comparative study of terminological dictionaries in the tourism sector showed that the lexicographic details used in these dictionaries can be divided into several groups. However, it should be noted that for Russian tourist terminology, this parameter, in our opinion, is quite important, since there are many borrowings among the terms of the tourism sector that are not fully assimilated by the language. Various grammatical information about the term can also be attributed to formal requisites. All analyzed Uzbek dictionaries lack such information. In some English-language publications, the term's part of speech and irregular forms of inflection are given. Information on phonetic, visual, morphological, and syntactic variants, as well as information about short and full variants of the term, are all included in the formal group. Almost all English-language dictionaries have graphic alternatives for area

affiliation (for example, traveler – US traveler) and short/long options (health tourism – health-care tourism).

Some Russian dictionaries, on the other hand, exclusively provide short and complete forms of nouns, such as tourist agent – travel agent. However, there are a great number of variances in Russian tourism terminology that, in our opinion, should be incorporated in dictionaries.

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The third set of requisites we identify, which is included in tourist terminological dictionaries, is referred to as attributive, and it contains multiple methods of attribution (to a certain lexical layer) of description units. Many English-language dictionaries include labels and indexes for the topic area or group to which this particular item belongs, such as hotel garni.

Areal details, or signs of the distinctive use of terms in individual places, are found in all English-language dictionaries (national interpretations). Essentially, the phrases are established and exclusively found in the United States or Europe, such as agency tour, which is a term used in the United States to represent a family vacation.

Many authors of the English-language dictionaries also give stylistic notes that allow us to highlight, in addition to terms, professionalism and jargon, for example: bucket shop – a slang term for a retail outlet selling cut-price wares, e.g., a travel agency which deals in unofficially discounted airline tickets, also known as discount ticket agency.

Some Russian dictionaries do not use attribute details. It is vital to focus on the peculiarities of the interpretation of tourist phrases when discussing the microcomposition of the analyzed dictionaries. Lexicographers pay close attention to this issue since explaining the meaning of a term in a dictionary is the most difficult and time-consuming task in most dictionaries. Almost all authors of English and Russian-language dictionaries use an encyclopedic definition to explain the meaning of a term, i.e., provide a detailed explanation based on a huge

quantity of extralinguistic explanatory material, such as: Attractions – things or activities which attract tourists, for example the CN Tower in Toronto, the tallest man-made free-standing structure, to be contrasted with the great natural attraction Niagara Falls. Business hotel – a specialized hotel for serving businessmen. The first business hotel was opened in 1908 in Buffalo (USA) by Ellsworth Statler under the name "Buffalo Statler" and provided businessmen with the maximum amenities for that time: the presence of individual door locks, running water, toilets, switches at the door, bathrooms in each room, a free morning newspaper. The fastest growing business hotel began to develop in the 20s. It was during this time that the world's largest hotel, Stephens, was built (1927), later renamed Conrad Hilton and marking the beginning of the Conrad Hilton empire in the hotel business.

Our observations also show that all English-language dictionaries provide available equivalents, including doublets and variants, while none of the analyzed Russian-language dictionaries provide this information.

Each unique lexicon is tailored to a distinct type of customer. As a result, during the dictionary creation phase, the dictionary user profile in the target dictionary should be generated. In this scenario, it's a good idea to figure out ahead of time what socio-cultural circumstances the dictionary will be used in and what information will be included in the dictionary [Fuentes-Olivera, p.A., 2009; 167–187]. It's worth noting that modern terminological dictionaries are created for a diverse range of possible readers. It is also stated that in a modern market economy, multifunctionality should be prioritized [Rossenbeck, Klaus, 2005; 189]. The following consumer groups [Isabel Balteiro] (examples are given in tourism industry) may need customized vocabulary.

→ specialists (developers of tourism statistics, i.e. experts involved in the implementation, editing and monitoring of tourism conditions, developers of tourism services and products)

→ semi-professionals (tour operators, travel agents and guides; tourism promotion representatives)

→ students (potential tourists and students studying at specialized universities)

→ intermediaries (intermediate group members such as translators, journalists and writers)

In sociolinguistic terms, scientific or technical terms are words that belong to a specific group of scientists or a community of experts. Since tourism is a sector of the economy and the production of goods and services, it would undoubtedly be

advisable to include the terminological system of tourism in the second group of terms.

Lexicographers can now develop dictionaries that are truly communicative, summarizing the most regularly used contexts of lexical units with the help of a ready-made language corpus. However, there is currently no such option for terminology. This is related to the fact that corporate language is not designed to function with words in specific contexts [Béjoint, Henri, 1988; 366]. Leading modern linguists have seen the formation of a special language corpus for scientific and technical phrases [Bowker, Lynne, and Jennifer Pearson, 2002].

Used dictionaries consist of the following typical macro-structural elements:

- Contents
- Introduction
- Organizations and individuals who work together and contribute to the creation
- of the vocabulary
- Covered Territory Names
- Operating instructions
- Dictionary section
- Applications

The macrostructure of a special lexicon should represent the involvement of specialists and organizations in its construction. While one specialist is sufficient for broad dictionaries, the construction of enhanced terminological dictionaries necessitates the collaboration of dozens of experts [Philip Durkin, 2016; 400].

Monolingual and bilingual specialized dictionaries may have nearly identical information representations in their macrostructures, but their microstructures follow different principles.

DISCUSSIONS

One-way or two-way bilingual special dictionaries are available. As a result of just one-way transformation, there are translated counterparts of the list of terms offered in one-way dictionaries (either from English to Uzbek, or from Uzbek to English). [Bergenholtz, 1995; 52] The majority of modern terminology dictionaries are one-way [Bergenholtz, 1995; 52]. Bilingual special dictionaries contain a broader set of functions, and they can be used to interpret information in foreign special contexts as well as provide new information, i.e. they are designed for both receptive and productive language practice, due to a two-way transformation. In practice, this can make them bulkier and more awkward to use. Some scholars disapprove of them because of these aspects [Yong, Heming and Jing Peng, 2007; 76]. The main premise of multilingual dictionaries is to select the

most straightforward option. In this scenario, a semantically equivalent word or phrase to the source language's unit is provided. Getting to the extreme alternative is, in fact, a difficult and nearly impossible undertaking. However, when it comes to scientific and technical terms, the chances of equivalence are high. The accomplishment of equivalence is hampered by an isomorphism (interlingual difference). However, there will be instances where one language's terminological system does not exist in another. Werner, who did research on the subject, notes the lack of a terminological system comparable to the one linked with Spanish coffee as an example. [Werner, Reinhold, 1999; 1868]. This is a natural phenomenon. There is no special coffee or coffee terminology in the Uzbek language either. This is because we do not have a coffee industry. But it is obvious that there is no such problem with the terminology of tourism, which is the object of our research. Eventually, this type of industry gained international popularity, and the number of languages that do not have their own terminological system for tourists is small. Another complication of the equivalence problem is that even in the context of the existence of a certain industry in both languages, the terminological systems of this industry are not systematized in the same way or closely because of national and cultural differences. At the same time, finding a balance in the content of notions is tough. This can be compared to the terms used in the realm of law. Rare technical terms or freshly developed terms are frequently connected with anisomorphism of certain phrases [Yong, Heming, and Jing Peng, 2007; 139]. This is a scenario that can be explained by the absence in the target language of a new notion that has not yet been accompanied by a new term, or a term that names a specific concept.

CONCLUSION

The way the elements of the dictionary's microstructure are displayed determines the dictionary's character. This necessitates the lexicographer putting himself in the shoes of a possible dictionary user, getting a sense of the application's complexities, and acting accordingly. The citation of transcription elements, for example, varies according to the type of active and inactive vocabulary. The user's primary purpose in passive dictionaries is to comprehend a spoken or written material. Naturally, the lexical unit's content is the most important factor here. The user looks up a term in the dictionary, chooses one of the existing values that matches the target's context, and interprets the text. The word's pronunciation and grammatical information are unimportant in this process. Indeed, other words in the context in which it interacts can provide information about its category and syntactic properties. The vast majority of language learners memorize new words,

work with texts, especially honing their pronunciation, and write them down in a separate notebook when it comes to pronunciation. As a result, even in passive dictionaries, this information appears alongside the lemma. It's worth noting that the user doesn't understand the language of the lemmas that make up such dictionaries, thus the translation is provided in his own tongue.

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